

DEFORMABILITY AND INTERNAL GEOMETRY OF TEXTILE REINFORCEMENTS AND LAMINATES

S.V. Lomov, M.Barburski*, T.Truong Chi and I.Verpoest

Department of Metallurgy and Material Science, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Kasteelpark Arenberg, 44, B-3001 Leuven, Belgium

** Department of Textile Architecture, Technical University of Lodz, Zeromskiego Street 116, 90-924 Lodz, Poland*

SUMMARY: The paper presents an approach to model the behaviour of a representative volume element (unit cell) of textile reinforcement in in-plane deformation and in compression. The model is a further development of a virtual textile concept implemented in the WiseTex software, and is based on a hierarchical description of textile properties and systematic application of the principle of minimum energy to calculate the textile geometry in the relaxed and deformed state. With the internal geometry of the unit cell built, the model computes overall parameters of the deformed textile, such as fibre volume fraction, porosity etc. The load-deformation curve is computed via the balance between change of the internal energy of the unit cell and mechanical work of the applied loads. The nesting of reinforcement in textile laminates is studied using a 3D geometrical model of a woven, braided and non-crimp stitched fabrics in the relaxed and sheared state.

KEY WORDS: Textile reinforcements, Tension, Shear, Compression, Internal geometry

1. INTRODUCTION

Deformability of textile preforms plays a key role in quality of a composite part formed into 3D shape and processed using Liquid Transfer Moulding (LTM) technique. Ill-chosen placement of the preform, disregarding its behaviour under large strain in complex deformation may result in the preform wrinkling or even damage, deteriorating the performance of the composite part. This explains an importance of predictive modelling of deformability of textile preforms. The deformation modes of primary importance are in-plane deformation (tension and shear) and compression of the preform. Deformability of woven preforms in these modes is the subject of the present paper.

2. GEOMETRY OF A WOVEN FABRIC IN RELAXED STATE

The comprehensive description of the model of the relaxed state of a woven fabric can be found elsewhere [1-5]. Here we state its main components used in simulation of the fabric deformation.

Figure 1. Elementary crimp interval of a woven fabric

A weave pattern (for one- and multilayered fabrics) is coded with matrix coding [1-4]. It allows separation of the crimped shape of the warp and weft yarns into elementary bent intervals (Figure 1), representing sections of the yarn between interlacing sites. The shape of the yarn on an elementary interval is described using a parameterised function $z(x;h/p)$, where z and x are coordinates of the yarn middle line, h is the crimp height and p is the distance between the interval ends (spacing of the yarns). The shape $z(x;h/p)$ for a given relative crimp height h/p is computed using the principle of minimum of bending energy of the yarn on the interval and has a form

$$z(x) = h[1/2 - 3(x/p)^2 + 4(x/p)^3 + A(h/p)(x/p)^2((x/p)-1)^2((x/p)-1/2)] \quad [1]$$

where the first term is a spline function, corresponding to the solution of the linearised minimum energy problem, and the second term represents a correction for a non-linear formulation. The function $A(h/p)$ is calculated from the solution of the minimum energy problem and is tabulated.

With this function known, the *characteristic function* F of the crimp interval is computed, representing the bending energy of the yarn:

$$w = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^p B(\kappa) \frac{(z'')^2}{(1+(z')^2)^{5/2}} dx = \frac{B(\bar{\kappa})}{p} F(h/p) \quad [2]$$

where $B(\kappa)$ is the (measured experimentally) bending rigidity of the yarn, which depends (non-linearly) on the local curvature $\kappa(x)$, or, after the integration, on an average curvature over the interval

$$\bar{\kappa} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{p} \int_0^p \frac{(z'')^2}{(1+(z')^2)^{5/2}} dx} \quad [3]$$

Function $F(h/p)$ is also tabulated. With the function F known, the transversal forces acting on the interval ends can be estimated as

$$Q = \frac{2w}{h} = \frac{2B(\bar{\kappa})}{p^2} \frac{p}{h} F(h/p) \quad [4]$$

Warp and weft yarns in the relaxed fabric are compressed by the transversal forces Q [4] according to experimental diagrams, measured on "virgin" yarns

$$d_1 = d_{10} \eta_1(Q), d_2 = d_{20} \eta_2(Q) \quad [5]$$

where subscript "0" refer to the uncompressed state of the yarn, d_1 and d_2 are dimensions of the yarn cross-section (Figure 1). These dimensions and crimp heights of the yarns are interconnected:

$$h^{Wa} = \Delta Z + (d^{Wa} + d^{We}) - (h_1^{Wa} + h_2^{We})/2 \quad [6]$$

where superscripts refer to the warp and weft yarns, subscripts "1" and "2" refer to two weft yarns in different layers, ΔZ is the distance between fabric layers (Figure 1).

With crimp heights of weft yarns given, equations [4-6] provide a closed system of non-linear equations for calculation of the transversal forces Q and yarn dimensions d_1 and d_2 . The weft crimp heights are found using the principle of minimum bending energy of the yarns inside the unit cell. Using [2], it is written as

$$W_{\Sigma} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{Wa}} \sum_{k=1}^{K_i^{Wa}} w_{ik}^{Wa} + \sum_{j=1}^{N_{We}} \sum_{k=1}^{K_j^{We}} w_{jk}^{We} \rightarrow \min \quad [7]$$

where subscripts i, j refer to different warp and weft yarns, k – to the elementary crimp interval of the warp/weft yarn. The minimum problem [7] is solved for the weft crimp heights, all other parameters defined inside the minimisation algorithm via solution of the system [4-6] for the given current crimp heights. It takes about 15s on Pentium II (405 MHz) PC to compute parameters for a 3D fabric with 20 yarns in the repeat, and about 0.5 s – for a plain weave fabric.

3. COMPRESSION

A comprehensive description of the compression model of a woven fabric can be found elsewhere [2]. Here we give an outline of the algorithm and discuss two issues not covered in that paper: behaviour of z-yarns in thick 3D fabrics and nesting of the layers in compression of laminate.

When a fabric is compressed, the following changes in geometry take place: (1) Warp and weft yarns are compressed; (2) The less crimped yarn system increases its crimp and vice versa. These two processes are treated in the model separately. To compute the compression of the yarns, the compression force per one intersection is evaluated:

$$Q_c = F / (N_{Wa} N_{We}) \quad [8]$$

where F is the pressure force on fabric repeat. This value is added to all the Q_{ij} – transversal forces acting on the intersections and computed with [4], to evaluate the dimensions of the yarns with [5]. Hence, both the compression due to yarn bending and the compression due to external force are accounted for. The algorithm presented above is then applied to yield the compressed dimensions of the yarn cross-sections and the new values of the yarn crimp. The change of crimp in compression (increasing for warp and decreasing for weft, or vice versa) leads to a decrease of the fabric thickness:

$$\text{work of compressive force } Q \text{ on change of thickness } db = \text{change of bending energy of yarns } dW \quad [9]$$

The compression of yarns has been accounted for before and the resulting changed cross-section dimensions are “frozen”, that’s why the work of yarn compression does not enter the balance [9].

Changes of the fabric thickness db and bending energy of the yarns dW depend on the change of the set of weft crimp heights $\{dh_j^{We}\}$ and therefore [9] has a set of unknown variables. A reasonable assumption to cope with this difficulty is: “The crimp changes in such a way as to provide the maximum possible change of thickness”. This means that if we consider the function $b(\{h_j^{We}\})$ (b being the fabric thickness) then changes of crimp will follow the direction of the maximum slope (in the opposite direction) $\{dh'_{jj}\} = -x \text{ grad } b(\{h_j^{We}\})$, where x is computed to satisfy [8]; slashed values refer to changed crimp. Equation [9] is then written as follows:

$$F \cdot [b(\{h_j^{We}\}) - b(\{h'_j{}^{We}\})] = \sum_{i,k} W^{Wa}(\{h'_j{}^{We}\}) + \sum_{j,k} W^{We}(\{h'_j{}^{We}\}) - \sum_{i,k} W^{Wa}(\{h_j^{We}\}) - \sum_{j,k} W^{We}(\{h_j^{We}\}) \quad [10a]$$

$$h'_j{}^{We} = h_j^{We} - x \cdot \text{grad} b(\{h_j^{We}\}) \quad [10b]$$

to be solved numerically for x , which should also satisfy

$$0 \leq h_j^{We} \leq h_j^{We,max}, \quad b(\{h_j^{We}\}) - b(\{h'_j{}^{We}\}) \geq 0 \quad [11]$$

The algorithm described above does not preserve the length of the yarns after compression, hence introducing an error on the final fabric geometry. In the compaction of a 2D fabric this error is small and can be considered to be negligible. When a 3D fabric is compacted, its z-yarns (going through the thickness), deviate considerably from their paths, as the length of the yarn must be preserved when the thickness of the fabric is reduced. In a 3D fabric with z-yarns initially almost vertical, they will acquire

Figure 2 Compression of 3D fabric. Above: Compression diagram, measured (lines) and computed (dots). Inlet: Computed and observed shape of z-yarn at 300 kPa

S/Z shapes. If the interlacing yarns are oblique, their initial sinusoidal shape is transformed into meander.

To describe such behaviour rigorously, one would have to account for all kinds of contacts between yarns occurring during the compaction. This task may be an interesting challenge for the finite element modelling. In the present model, a simple geometrical approach is followed. A spline correction is added to the yarn path, with a factor chosen as to preserve the yarn length after the deformation. Figure 2 shows the results of measurement and simulation of compression of 3D glass fabric (yarns 4x4x33 tex, 35 yarns/cm in warp and weft, areal density 3900 g/m², weave is shown in Figure 2). The fabric is proposed in [6] as a benchmarking case for study of LTM composite processing. Compression of the fabric has been measured on the KES-F textile compression tester for the low load range and on Instron for higher loads. The input data on compressibility of the yarns and their bending rigidity has been measured on KES-F. Other fabric data was taken as specified in [6]. The described algorithm provides a reasonable prediction of the compression diagram as well as the fabric internal structure after compression.

In composites forming processes normally stacked 2D fabric layers are compressed to form a plate or a 3D shaped laminate. It is well known that due to nesting of the fabric layers thickness of the laminate per one layer is decreasing with the number of layers (for a given pressure) [2, 7, 8] (there exists an evidence of an anomalous opposite behaviour [9]). The presented model of the fabric geometry and compression accounts for this fact. Consider a plain woven glass fabric, made of glass rovings 480 tex, with the yarn density of 36/34 yarns/cm.

The fabric has been thoroughly studied in [2, 4], where additional information can be found. In these papers a *WiseTex* model of the fabric geometry and compression has been verified against experimental data. Consider a laminate made out of L layers of this fabric, compressed at a given pressure. The layers are randomly shifted relative to each other and nested. The nesting algorithm searches for the minimum vertical coordinate of a layer mid-plane when it is just in contact with the layer beneath it. Figure 3 shows the results of a Monte-Carlo calculation of the average thickness of the laminate (500 runs), at pressure 100 kbar (compression of the fabric taken into account). The results correspond very well with the experimental variation of the thickness with the number of layers, measured in compression tests.

4. TENSION

Consider first a woven fabric under bi-axial tension characterised by deformations in warp (x -axis) and weft (y -axis) directions $e_x = Y/Y_0 - 1$, $e_y = X/X_0 - 1$, where X and Y are sizes of the fabric repeat, subscript "0" designates the undeformed state. As discussed above, inside the *WiseTex* model the internal structure of the fabric is described based on weft crimp heights h_j^{we} and weft and warp cross-section dimensions at the intersections d_{ij}^{wa} and d_{ji}^{we} (subscripts designate different yarns in the fabric repeat). These values change after the deformation. Tension of the yarns induces

transversal forces, which compress the yarns, changing d 's. The same transversal forces change the equilibrium conditions between warp and weft, which leads to a redistribution of crimp and change of crimp heights. When the mentioned values in the deformed configuration are computed, the internal geometry of the deformed fabric is built using the *WiseTex* algorithms as explained above. Change of length of the yarns determines their average (in the repeat) deformations, which, through the tension-deformation diagrams of the yarns allow computing tensions of the yarns. When summed up, with yarns inclinations due to the crimp accounted for, the yarn tensions are transformed into loads, caused the fabric deformations. This computational scheme has been proposed for plain weaves in 70s and also recently implemented via FEA (see the Introduction); the present implementation of it puts it into the scope of *WiseTex* modelling, covering a wide range of woven structures.

The key problem in the bi-axial modelling is computation of crimp heights and transversal forces in the deformed structure. Assuming that the spacing of the yarns in the fabric is changed proportionally to the change of the repeat size, we compute the x and y positions of intersections of warp and weft in the deformed structure. The configuration of the yarns in the crimp intervals between the intersections is determined by these positions and (unknown) crimp heights. Consider some values of the crimp heights. Then the *WiseTex* geometrical model determines positions of the ends of crimp intervals (warp/weft intersections) and bent shape of the yarns in the intervals. The transversal forces are computed then using the following formula (Figure 4):

$$Q = Q_{bend} + T_1 \sin \theta_1 + T_2 \sin \theta_2 \quad [12]$$

where Q_{bend} is the transversal force due to the yarn bending [4], $T_{1,2}$ are the yarn tensions on two crimp intervals adjacent to the point of application of the transversal force, $\theta_{1,2}$ are the angles of inclination of the yarn on these crimp intervals. We assume that the tension of the yarn can be computed based on the average deformation ε of the yarns (therefore $T_1=T_2$): $T_1 = T_2 = T(\varepsilon)$, $\varepsilon = (l - l_0)/l_0$, where l is

the yarn length. Note that T depends on yarn length after the deformation, which in its turn depend on crimp heights and yarn dimensions.

The transversal forces compress the yarns according to an experimental law of the compression [5]. When the yarn dimensions are computed and "frozen", then crimp heights are determined using

the minimum energy condition: $W = W_{bend} + W_{tens} \rightarrow \min$, where W_{bend} and W_{tens} are the bending and tension energy of the yarns. The former is computed summing up bending energies of the yarns in crimp intervals between yarn intersections [7], the latter is the sum of tension energies of all the yarns, which are computed using their (linear or non-linear) tension diagrams and yarn deformations.

The computations described above determine one step in the iteration process: starting from current values of the crimp heights we compute yarn lengths, yarn tensions, transversal forces, yarn compressed dimensions and then new values of the crimp heights. If one side of the fabric is kept free (uni-axial tension, say, along the warp), then the described algorithm has another, the outmost iteration loop, searching for $X < X_0$ (negative e_y) which would lead to zero loads along weft (y) direction. This allows computing Poisson coefficient for the fabric.

Experimental bi-axial tensile properties of the same plain woven glass fabrics have been tested on the biaxial tensile machine of the Department MTM. *WiseTex* modelling of the tension of the fabrics, described above, have been performed. The yarn tension resistance was assumed to be the sum of

tension resistance of the fibres. Bending rigidity of the yarns has been measured on KES-F to provide

the value of 0.44 N mm^2 .

Figure 5 shows the results of the calculations. We can conclude that calculations describe well the qualitative difference between deformation regimes of uniaxial and biaxial tension, and provide reasonable quantitative prediction of the diagrams. One of the sources of the difference between the measured and the calculated diagrams can be the fact that the measured average strain between grips can be larger than the strain in the middle of the sample.

5. SHEAR

When a woven fabric is sheared, the orthogonal directions of warp and weft become skewed. Such a configuration is similar to a braided structure. A model for internal geometry of braids is proposed in [Lomov, in print #610] and is used to construct the sheared woven fabric internal geometry.

The most important feature of non-orthogonal unit cell of a sheared fabric is the presence of twist of the yarns. The twist is evident in cross-sections of non-orthogonal fabrics and can be mathematically described using the algorithms of [Lomov, in print #610]. As shown in this paper, the twist can be considerable, attaining the values as high as $30\text{-}40^\circ$.

In formulating the model of the shear forces we follow the lines sketched by S.Kawabata in 70s [10-12], which are also followed by more recent publications [13-16].

Consider a sheared unit cell of a woven fabric (Figure 6). For simplicity the illustrations below show a plain weave unit cell. The equations are however applied to elementary crimp intervals and the forces are summed up for the actual fabric repeat. An account is taken therefore of the differences imposed by the weave pattern, as shown in comparison with experimental data below.

Our aim is, given a value of the shear angle, γ , compute the shear force, T , in the presence of (pre)tension of the fabric. The tension is dealt with according to the algorithms of the previous section, resulting in values of the tension of yarns and transversal forces Q , associated with it [12].

The shear force T is related to a moment M at the point O and to the mechanical force A done at the shear deformation:

$$M = 2TXY \cos \gamma; \quad A = \frac{1}{2} M \gamma \quad [14]$$

We will take into account the following mechanisms of the yarns deformation, determining the shear resistance: (1) Friction; (2) (Un)bending; (3) Lateral compression; (4) Torsion; (5) Vertical displacement. Accordingly the mechanical work A , moment M and shear force T are subdivided:

$$A = A_{friction} + A_{disp} + A_{bending} + A_{torsion} \quad [15]$$

The lateral compression of the yarns is introduced via the transversal forces. We do not consider intra-yarn friction here, as suggested in [17]. It is felt that this factor is accounted for by the lateral compression calculations, but the question needs more careful examination in future work.

The transversal forces, acting on the yarns, and determining the friction between them, are caused by tension and bending of the yarns, as we have seen before [12]. During the shear, yarns are subject of lateral compression. This will certainly happen after the locking angle is reached: $\gamma^* = \arccos(w/p)$, where w is the yarn width, p is the spacing [18, 19]. The lateral compression is present also before this moment, under a pressure of crimped interlaced warp and weft yarns. The lateral compression creates a pressure inside yarns, which results in an additional component of the transversal force acting on the yarns of the interlacing system. Therefore the transversal forces at yarns intersections will be

$$Q = Q_{bending} + Q_{tension} + Q_{compression} \quad [16]$$

where the first two terms are computed with [4] and [12].

The last term in [16] is computed based on the change of fibre volume fraction in the deformed configuration (Figure 7). The geometric algorithm for non-orthogonal unit cell provides change of the shape of yarn cross-section

and therefore the change of the fibre volume fraction. The pressure P inside the yarn and the transversal force are computed then using the experimental compression diagram of the yarn:

$$Q_{compression} = (P_{Wa} + P_{We}) \cdot d_2^{Wa} d_2^{We}; P = P(Vf(d_1^{new}, d_2^{new})) \quad [17]$$

where the superscripts “Wa” and “We” designate two intersecting yarns.

The components of the shear resistance are computed as follows.

$$\text{Friction moment: } M_{friction} = fQr; r = \frac{2R}{3}; R = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{d_{Wa2} d_{We2}} \quad [18]$$

where f is the coefficient of friction, r – effective radius of the zone of friction for the normal force Q evenly distributed over a circle with radius R , d_2 is width of the intersecting warp and weft yarns.

$$\text{Mechanical work of torsion: } A_{torsion} = \frac{1}{2} C \tau^2; \tau = \int_0^s \mathbf{t} \cdot \left(\mathbf{a} \times \frac{d\mathbf{a}}{ds} \right) ds \quad [19]$$

where C is the torsional rigidity of the yarn, τ is the full angle of torsion, computed by integration of rotation of vector \mathbf{a} , determining orientations of the yarn cross-section axis, about the tangent to the yarn middle line \mathbf{t} , over the yarn length. The torsional rigidity of the yarn can be estimated as

$$C = \frac{B}{d_1 / 2} \quad [20]$$

where B is the bending rigidity of the yarn, d_1 – its thickness [20].

$$\text{Mechanical work of (un)bending of the yarns: } A_{bending} = \frac{1}{2} B \int_0^s \left(\frac{d^2 \delta \mathbf{z}}{ds^2} \right)^2 ds \quad [21]$$

where δz is the difference between z -coordinate of the centre line of the yarn before and after the deformation (at a given coordinate along the yarn s).

Mechanical work of vertical displacement of the yarns (this displacement goes against the transversal forces Q):

$$A_{disp} = Q \cdot \frac{1}{l} \int_{contact} \delta z \cdot ds \quad [22]$$

where l is the yarn length, and the integration is performed over the contact zones between warp and weft yarns, determined by the geometrical model [4, 21].

Figure.8 shows the results of simulation of the initial study of shear for a twill 1/3 glass (480 tex) fabric. The experimental curve was measured on KES-F shear tester. Bending properties of the yarns and friction coefficient was also measured on KES-F, resulting in the following values: $B = 0.25 \text{ N mm}^2$, $f = 0.24$. The results of compression tests on the yarns and yarn dimensions are given and discussed in [2]. Torsional rigidity of the yarns was estimated with [20]. The comparison of the calculations and experimental values is quite satisfactory for this low shear region.

Figure 8. KES-F shear diagram of glass plain and twill fabric.

Calculations for larger shear angles produce qualitatively satisfactory results, representing the main features of the shear process: fast increase of the shear force when the angle of shear increases to a locking state, increase of the fabric thickness for large shear angles due to the lateral compression of the yarns. However, quantitative comparison with shear frame experiments should involve careful control over parameters of the experiment, especially (pre)tension of the sample [18, 19] and will be a subject of future work. The model in the present formulation is not robust: it is sensitive to the variations of the input parameters, such as coefficient of friction or compression diagrams, which are measured with significant scatter.

Figure 9. Properties of glass rovings. Dimensions of cross-sections (measurements for rovings of different linear density and master curve)

To assess the sensitivity of the model to variations of parameters, consider a set of numerical experiments: simulations of shear of glass plain woven fabrics. Available literature data [2, 18, 19] and special measurements of parameters of glass rovings allow establishing of a set of master curves for estimation of dimensions of cross-sections, bending rigidity and compression curve of a glass roving with given linear density. The averaged curves, shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10, were used to

determine input data for three types of yarns: 500, 1000 and 2000 tex. Fabrics with different spacing of the yarns (inverse to the ends/picks count) were considered, the ratio of the spacing to the yarn width being 0.6, 0.75 and 0.9. This ratio characterises the tightness of the fabric. Friction coefficient was set to be 0.2 in all the cases.

Figure 11 depicts the results of calculation of shear resistance of these fabrics. The model represents qualitatively the behaviour of the plain woven fabrics in shear: fast increase of the shear force for high shear angles, deformability of the fabric beyond the locking angle. Shear resistance increases with the yarn linear density for the same fabric tightness. Fabric tightness plays a definitive role between factors determining the shear resistance.

6. CONCLUSION

We have presented a family of models of internal structure of woven fabrics in relaxed and deformed state and of the load-deformation response for compression, bi- and uniaxial tension and shear. The models are based on the following common principles:

- Description of the 2D and 3D weaves by a unified matrix coding methodology;
- Decomposition of the crimped shape of the yarns into a set of elementary crimp intervals, with the shape of each interval corresponds to the solution of the minimum bending energy problem;
- Calculation of the compressed dimensions of the yarn cross-sections by the balance between transversal forces generated by bending of the yarns and compression resistance of the yarns;
- Calculation of the crimp heights of the yarns via a solution of minimum energy problem.

The models are implemented in *WiseTex* software package. The results of the simulations have been compared with the experimental observations and finite element simulations, resulting in a satisfactory agreement between them. However, more work has to be done to achieve robust and reliable predictions of the load-deformation curves. A bottleneck here is creation of a database of

measurements of properties of yarns in bending and compression, which can be readily used for predictive simulations of behaviour of preforms in composite forming.

The internal geometry description after deformation can further fed into flow modelling software, which allows computing local permeability of the deformed reinforcement, and micro-mechanical modelling to calculate homogenised local stiffness of the composite. This opens way to creation an integrated design software tool, combining *local meso-analysis* on the scale level of unit cell, *homogenisation*, resulting in permeability/stiffness parameters varying according to the local deformations and *macro analysis* of the filling/mechanical properties of the composite part.

7. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The work reported here is going on in the scope of the projects "Technologies for Carbon Fibre Reinforced Modular Automotive Body Structures" (TECABS, Brite-Euram), funded by the European Commission (EC), "Concurrent multi-scale design/engineering of textile composites" (OT), funded by the Flemish Government through the Research Council of K.U.Leuven. MB worked in KUL as a Marie Curie Fellow of EC, being a PhD student of TU Lodz under a supervision of Prof. J.Masajtis. 3D fabric of the section 3 was provided by Prof. R.S.Parnas, University of Connecticut, USA. The authors would like to thank Dr.J.Laperre and Dr.D.Verstraete of Centexbel, Belgium for providing the opportunity to use the KES-F equipment.

8. REFERENCES

1. Lomov, S.V., G. Huysmans, Y. Luo, R. Parnas, A. Prodromou, I. Verpoest, and F.R. Phelan, Composites part A. **32** (2001) 1379-1394
2. Lomov, S.V. and I. Verpoest, Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites. **19** (2000) 1329-1350
3. Lomov, S.V., G. Huysmans, and I. Verpoest, Textile Research Journal. **71** (2001) 534-543
4. Lomov, S.V., A.V. Gusakov, G. Huysmans, A. Prodromou, and I. Verpoest, Composites Science and Technology. **60** (2000) 2083-2095
5. Belov, E.B., S.V. Lomov, I. Verpoest, T. Peters, D. Roose, R.S. Parnas, K. Hoes, and V. Sol, Composites Science and Technology (submitted)
6. Parnas, R.S., J.G. Howard, T.L. Luce, and S.G. Adwani, Polymer Composites. **16** (1995) 429-445
7. Luo, Y. and I. Verpoest, Polymer Composites. **20** (1999) 179-191
8. Chen, B. and T.-W. Chou, Composites Science and Technology. **60** (2000) 2223-2231
9. Pearce, N. and J. Summerscales, Composites Manufacturing. **6** (1995) 15-21
10. Kawabata, S., M. Niwa, and H. Kawai, Journal of the Textile Institute. **64** (1973) 21-46
11. Kawabata, S., M. Niwa, and H. Kawai, Journal of the Textile Institute. **64** (1973) 47-61
12. Kawabata, S., M. Niwa, and H. Kawai, Journal of the Textile Institute. **64** (1973) 42-85
13. Long, A., International Conference on Virtual Prototyping EUROPAM 2000, Nantes. 1-17.(2000)
14. Long, A.C., M.J. Clifford, P. Harrison, and C.D. Rudd, ICMAC - International Conference for Manufacturing of Advanced Composites, Belfast. 66-76.(2001)
15. Long, A.C., F. Robitaille, B.J. Souter, and C.D. Rudd. 13th International Conference on Composite Materials (ICCM-13), Beijing, China(2001).
16. Crookston, J.J., A.C. Long, and I.A. Jones, Plastics, Rubber and Composites. **31** (2002) 58-65
17. Harrison, P., M.J. Clifford, A.C. Long, and C.D. Rudd, Proceedings of the 5th International ESAFORM Conference on Material Forming, Krakow. 275-278.(2002)
18. Long, A.C., Composites part A. **32** (2001) 941-953
19. Long, A.C., B.J. Souter, F. Robitaille, and C.D. Rudd, Plastics, Rubber and Composites. **31** (2002) 87-97
20. Morton, W. and D.W.S. Hearle, Mechanical properties of textile fibres. 1970.
21. Lomov, S.V., G. Huysmans, Y. Luo, A. Prodromou, I. Verpoest, and A.V. Gusakov. 9th European Conference on Composite Materials (ECCM-9), Brighton(2000).